

Spectroscopic studies of some VO^{II} complexes

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Manuscript received 11 April 2007, revised 14 November 2007, accepted 26 November 2007

Abstract : The reaction of 2-formylpyridine semicarbazone (HFPS), 2-formylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (HFPTS), 2-acetylpyridine semicarbazone (HAPS) and 2-acetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (HAPTS) with VOSO₄ in ethanolic solution affords the complexes of formula VOL₂, where L = FPS, APS, FPTS and APTS. The infrared spectra of complexes in comparison to that of the free ligand show the mode of coordination of the ligands. The appearance of three bands in their electronic spectra is indicative of their square pyramidal geometry which is further substantiated by their electron spin resonance spectra. The presence of eight lines in the hyperfine ESR spectra shows that they are mononuclear complexes.

Keywords : VO^{II} complexes, semicarbazone, ESR spectra.

Introduction

In the recent decade hydrazones and carbazones compounds have invited the attention of chemists and biochemists to a greater extent due to their interesting biological activities. It was Domagk and his co-workers who first of all in 1946 made a vital report regarding the biological activities associated with carbazones like semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones¹. Since then several reports have been made on the antimicrobial, antiviral and antitumour activities of carbazones²⁻⁴. Cu^{II} complexes with 2-oxybutanaldehyde thiosemicarbazone show antitumour activity *in vivo* and the cytotoxicity *in vitro*⁵. However, there is only a little work has been done on the structural aspects of transition metal complexes of carbazones which may be correlated to their biological activities. This made our pursuit to make studies on the structural aspects of transition metal complexes with biologically active ligands i.e. carbazones and thiosemicarbazones followed by the studies of their biological activities in comparison to the free ligands. The present paper reports the structural aspects of complexes of VO^{II} with 2-formylpyridine semicarbazone (HFPS), 2-acetylpyridine semicarbazone (HAPS), 2-formylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (HFPTS) and 2-acetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (HAPTS) on the basis of their electronic spectra and electron spin resonance spectra.

Results and discussion

All the complexes are coloured and insoluble in water but soluble in chloroform and DMF. On the basis of the

data obtained from their element analysis, complexes were formulated as (VOL₂), where L = FPS, APS, FPTS and APTS. The very low values of their molar conductivity (around 12.00–20.00 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) in DMF suggest their non-electrolytic nature⁶. Their μ_{eff} values around 1.8 B.M. at room temperature shows the presence of an unpaired electron in the complexes.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of the complexes were compared with that of the free ligands to ascertain the mode of coordination of the ligands to the metal ion. The free ligand absorbs strongly at 3440 cm⁻¹ due to stretching vibration of -NH₂ group which does not undergo any significant change in complexes. It shows the non-participation of -NH₂ in coordination. In the IR spectra of all the free ligands a strong band appears at 1620–1635 cm⁻¹ due to γ(C=N) of the azomethyne group. This band doesn't undergo low energy shift in complexes indicating its non-participation in coordination^{7,8}. The band at 1670–1680 cm⁻¹ due to γ(C=O) of the free ligands (HFPS and HAPS)⁹⁻¹² is observed also in the spectra of complexes (I) and (II). This shows the non-involvement of carbonyl oxygen in coordination. The ligand shows strong multiple absorptions centred at 1530 cm⁻¹ probably due to the combination of γ(C=N) and δ(NH). This band disappears in the spectra of all the complexes which suggests the deprotonation as well as coordination of -NH group to metal ions. The absorption bands at 1470 cm⁻¹ and 1300 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the free ligand are assigned to γ(C=S) + γ(C-N) + δ(NH₂). These bands do not show

any considerable shift in the spectra of complexes. The typical strong absorption band due to $\gamma(\text{C}=\text{S})$ of the ligand at 825 cm^{-1} also remains intact in the spectra of the complexes (III) and (IV) which is indicative of the non-participation of S in coordination. The bands at 1590 and 1570 cm^{-1} of the free ligand are identified as γPy (I) and $\gamma\text{P}\gamma$ (II) absorption bands due to pyridine ring vibrations in complexes¹³⁻¹⁵. These bands uniformly shift to higher frequencies in complexes showing the involvement of heterocyclic nitrogen in coordination. The presence of M-N bonding in complexes is further substantiated by the appearance of new bands at $960-985\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\gamma(\text{M}-\text{N})$ vibration in the spectra of the complexes¹⁶⁻¹⁸. In addition to these bands the complexes display a strong band at $962-985\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\gamma(\text{V}=\text{O})$ vibration¹⁹⁻²¹.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the complexes exhibit three bands as given in Table 1.

Complexes	$\gamma\text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$	$\gamma\text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$	$\gamma\text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$
I VO(FPS) ₂	11.500	17.300	23.300
II VO(APS) ₂	12.200	16.880	19.230
III VO(FPTS) ₂	11.800	18.800	22.000
IV VO(APTS) ₂	12.000	18.000	20.000

The appearance of three bands in the electronic spectra of VO^{II} i.e. a d¹ system (²D-term) is a strong evidence in the favour of square pyramidal symmetry around V^{IV} ion²². The energy order of various crystal fields terms of ²D-term under the square pyramidal crystal field is given as :

$${}^2B_2 < {}^2E_2 < {}^2B_1 < {}^2A_1$$

Fig. 1. 8-Lines EPR spectrum of VO(FPS)₂.

The three absorption bands in the electronic spectra of the complexes may be assigned to the following transitions.

(I) ${}^2E \leftarrow {}^2B_2(\gamma)$, (II) ${}^2B_1 \leftarrow {}^2B_2(\gamma_2)$ and (III) ${}^2A_1 \leftarrow {}^2B_2(\gamma_3)$

The different crystal field parameters were calculated on the basis of absorption frequencies of the three different bands in electronic spectra of the complexes which were found in good agreement with the reported values for VO^{II} complexes of C_{4v} symmetry^{15,21,23-26}.

The values of the different parameters, i.e. $10Dq$, Ds and Dt are given in Table 2.

Complexes	$Dq\text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$	$Ds\text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$	$Dt\text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$
I VO(FPS) ₂	17.300	-2.457	826
II VO(APS) ₂	16.880	-2.456	916
III VO(FPTS) ₂	18.000	-2.200	1040
IV VO(APTS) ₂	18.000	-2.000	1200

Ds and Dt are defined as second order radial integral and fourth order radial integral respectively and they define the distortion in complexes from the regular symmetry²⁷. For all the four complexes, Ds values are negative which lead to the positive $d\sigma$ and $d\pi$ parameters of angular overlap which are consistent with known compressed structure along Z-axis of a complex. This shows that in all the four complexes the V=O bond length is shorter than the other four M-L bond length^{27,28}.

Electron spin resonance spectra :

The ESR spectra of VO^{II} complexes exhibit Lorentzian type of peaks which consist of eight lines due to hyperfine splitting of the spectral line by the interaction with nuclear spin $I = 7/2$ and hence the number of lines = $2nl + 1 = 2 \times 1 \times 7/2 + 1 = 8$. This shows the presence of only one vanadium

ion in the complexes and hence, they are mono nuclear complexes. The various ESR parameter i.e. g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , $|g|$, A_{\parallel} , A_{\perp} and $|A|$ were calculated from ESR spectra of the complexes. Values of $|g|$ were calculated ($g_{\parallel} + 2g_{\perp}$) and $|A|$ by $1/3(A_{\parallel} + A_{\perp})$. The different values are given in the Table 3 and EPR spectrum is shown in the Fig. 1.

Table 3

		g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	$ g $	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}	$ A $
I	VO(FPS) ₂	1.969	2.005	1.993	158.57	64.28	95.71
II	VO(APS) ₂	1.962	1.991	1.981	171.42	57.85	9.70
III	VO(FPTS) ₂	1.966	1.993	1.984	171.42	58.57	96.18
IV	VO(APTS) ₂	1.960	2.005	1.990	171.28	57.14	96.18

The values of the different ESR spectral parameters are in the fair agreement with the values reported for square pyramidal symmetry of the complexes²⁹⁻³¹.

The value of g_{\parallel} shows the appreciable covalent character in the metal ligand bond.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The ligands were prepared by the reported method³². 0.02 mole of ligands (about 0.27–0.33 g) was dissolved in 15 ml of ethanol to which 15 ml of ethanol containing 0.01 mole (~0.24 g) of VOSO₄·5H₂O was added. The resulting solution was refluxed for 2–4 h. The pH of the medium was maintained about 8. On cooling the solution a light green mass appeared which was filtered and was washed with ethanol. It was dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ in desiccator. The yield was found ~75–80%. The element analysis was carried out by usual methods. The electronic spectra (CHCl₃) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-Lambda-2B spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-1620 FT-IR spectrophotometer. ESR spectra were recorded on a Varian E-lin, Century series spectrometer equipped with a dual cavity and operating at X-band 100 KHz modulation. Solid diphenylpicryl hydrazyl (DPPH) was used as field marker. The magnetic moment was measured at room temperature using Gouy's technique.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors, Dr. Rajeeva Ranjan is thankful to Aglomed Pharmaceutical for financial support.

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